

A Clinical Study on Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty in a Tertiary Care Centre**Bhumireddy Chandrasekhar Reddy¹, Ankireddypalle Vijay Bhaskar Reddy²,
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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Hemorrhoidectomy is one of the most common surgical procedures performed routinely, and with the advances in Laser technology Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty is now an alternative to open method.

The aim of this study was to determine the outcomes and postoperative complications of Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty.

Patients and Methods: It was a Prospective Observational study done in 40 cases selected by Systemic Random Sampling method in those attending the General Surgery Outpatient Department in a Tertiary Care centre, for Laser Hemorrhoidectomy during a period of 6 months. Post operatively patients were followed for 12 months. Duration of the procedure, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain, and the resolution of hemorrhoids, and recurrence of hemorrhoids were analyzed.**Results:** In the study male patients were 60% and female cases were 40%. 65% of patients were in the age group of 40 – 50 years. Average intra operative time was 23min. There were no significant intra operative complications. Post operatively pain was less as per Visual Analogue Scale. There was no rectal tenesmus or alteration of defecation habits. Hemorrhoid symptoms and size reached approximately three to four months post-procedure. The frequency of pain, bleeding, pruritus ani, were decreased by 75-80%. There was a significant reduction in hemorrhoids with the rate of recurrence being 7% over 12 months of follow-up.**Conclusion:** Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty is a safe procedure, not associated with any excessive postoperative complications. It improves patient's quality of life and can be a substitution of other surgical methods and as a day care procedure.**Keywords:** Open Hemorrhoidectomy, Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty, Complications.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Hemorrhoids are one of the most common among colorectal diseases, with prevalence ranging from 3% to 29% with more than 4% of the symptomatic population. [1] Male are more frequently affected than females. Hemorrhoids are graded into different grades from 1 to 4. Grade 1 is seen as a congested vein on an anoscopic examination. Grade 2 is prolapsed but reduces spontaneously. Grade 3 hemorrhoids are prolapsed but require manual reduction whereas grade 4 are irreducible. [2] The most common symptoms are pain, bleeding, Pruritus ani, prolapse, or mucosal discharge. There are many methods of treatment ranging from conservative, band ligation, sclerotherapy, stapled hemorrhoidopexy, and laser photocoagulation to Milligan Morgan method.

Milligan Morgan method is the gold standard and most frequently used procedure. However, postoperative pain, hemorrhage, urinary retention, and abscess formation are the most common side effects associated with this. The long-term complications include stool incontinence, fistula

formation, and stenosis. [3,4] Because of these drawbacks, Burch et al. have come up with a new no excisional surgical procedure known as Hemorrhoidal laser procedure. [5] It is minimally invasive and mostly suitable for a symptomatic second to third-degree hemorrhoids. With Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty it is possible to get a significant reduction and shrinkage of final branches of the superior hemorrhoidal artery. [6,7] Using lasers in the treatment of hemorrhoid leads to minimal tissue damage and good hemostasis, and it can also reduce the duration of surgery and hospital stay. However, against all the benefits, specific training and precaution measurements are required to use lasers in therapy. Moreover, to protect their eyes from invisible lights produced by laser, it is a must that the surgeons use goggles. [8,9]

The aim of this study is to determine the outcomes and postoperative complications of Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty in terms of duration of the procedure, intraoperative complications, postoperative pain, and the declivity of

hemorrhoids, persistency or complete resolution, and recurrence of hemorrhoids.

Patients and Method

This was a prospective observational study done in a tertiary care centre over a period of 6 months in 40 cases with a follow-up of 12 months. All patients underwent the Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty. Informed and written consent was taken for all patients considered for the study.

Preoperatively, patients underwent thorough evaluation, and digital rectal and proctoscopic examinations. Patients with second and third-degree hemorrhoids were admitted for the Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty.

Patients younger than 18 years and older than 75 years with complete rectal prolapsed, thrombosed hemorrhoids, fecal incontinence, anal stenosis anal fissure, anal fistula, acute inflammatory bowel disease were excluded from the study. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institute Ethical Committee.

Time taken for the procedure, preoperative complications (bleeding), postoperative pain, resolution of hemorrhoids, and relapse were collected. A visual analogue scale was used to evaluate 4 points (no, mild, moderate, severe) postoperative pain. No pain was evaluated as zero mild pain=1, moderated=2, severe=3 on the scale. All patients were evaluated 7 days and 28 days post operating then at three months, six months, and nine months, 12 months post-surgery.

The patient is placed in the lithotomy position. The surgical site is thoroughly cleaned, prepared, and draped to maintain sterility. A disposable proctoscope is gently inserted into the anal canal to visualize the Hemorrhoid masses.

All the surgeries were performed using the Lasotronix 1470. Using a bare fiber laser, 60–70 joules of energy is sprayed onto the mucosa at the apex of the Hemorrhoidal mass from the inside. The laser fiber is directed into the Intersphincteric space, where an additional 60–70 joules of energy is applied to the apex of the Hemorrhoidal mass. The laser fiber is inserted directly into the Hemorrhoidal mass, delivering 120–180 joules of energy, depending on the size and extent of the hemorrhoid. The same procedure is performed for all identified Hemorrhoidal masses.

Post-laser Care: Ice is applied to each treated hemorrhoidal mass immediately after the laser procedure to reduce swelling and soothe the tissues. The procedure is completed once all hemorrhoidal masses are treated. This method ensures precise targeting of hemorrhoidal tissue with minimal

damage to surrounding structures, promoting faster healing and recovery. Proctoscope was performed prior to surgery with the patient in the lithotomy position after general or spinal anesthesia. No antibiotics were routinely used. No bowel preparation was done prior to surgery.

Statistical analysis was done using SPSS 1. Mean, averages and percentages were used to describe the variables and p value was calculated where need and Less than 0.05 of the P-value was considered statistically significant.

Results

In our study of 40 cases 24(60%) were male and 16 (40%) were female. Youngest age of the patient was 21 years and the elderly one was 68years. Majority of the cases (65%) were between 40-50yers of age. The median age of the participants was 45 years. Among the 40 cases 15 (38%) had Grade 3 Hemorrhoids and 25 (62%) had Grade 2 Hemorrhoids.

Bleeding during defecation was the main complaint in all the cases (100%) and pain was seen in 17 cases (42.5%), perianal discharge and itching was seen in 15 cases(38%). 12 cases operated under General anesthesia and rest were done under regional anesthesia. The average operative time from positioning to completion was around 23 minutes.

There were no significant intraoperative complications. Post operatively 5 cases (12.5%) had bleeding and 4 among these were managed by laser again under sedation, but one case suture was taken to control the bleeding. Patients were discharged on the same except the 5 cases after 6 hours hospital stay. The cases with bleeding were discharged on the next day morning.

Patients were followed up on post-operative day 1, after 1 month, 3 months, six months and 12 months. Visual analogue scale was used for assessment of pain.

On post-operative day 1, 85% cases had mild pain, 7% cases had moderate pain and 8% cases had severe pain. Oral and intramuscular or intravenous analgesics were given and the pain was controlled. At the end of one month 95% cases no pain and 5% had mild pain. On 3rd, 6th and 12th month follow up none had pain.

Bleeding was noted in 5 cases on day 1 and none had bleeding in the subsequent follow ups. Size of the hemorrhoids in grade 2 was reduced in 3 months and grade 3 reduction was noted in 6 months follow up. None of the cases had fistula or incontinence, stenosis or abscess.

Pre-operative Hemorrhoid mass

Picture on Post-Operative Day 1

Picture on 1 month post operatively

Picture on 3 months post operatively

Figure 1:

Discussion

The desire of patient and surgeon is to have an uncomplicated Hemorrhoidectomy. The complications of surgery are postoperative pain, bleeding, and hospital stay timely return of the patient to daily activities and, thus, enhance the quality of life.

The Hemorrhoidal artery ligation (HAL) via the Doppler route is a relatively modern procedure. Maria et al. validated in their research that HAL is a secure and practically potent substitute procedure to conventional hemorrhoidectomy. [10] Pucher et al. proposed a non-excisional mini-invasive surgical method called Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty. [11] In this study Laser Hemorrhoidoplasty procedure showed remarkably good results in terms of post operative symptoms and recurrences. Due to lack of vascular connection and flow to pile mass, there is a significant reduction of pile mass and betterment of symptoms. [12] Laser coagulation of vessels has the advantage of conservation of anatomy and physiology of anal canal, compared to other forms of treatment. Thus, it minimizes post-operative impaired anal function. [13]

Due to the highly selective effects of laser beams effect on arteries, the damage caused to the surrounding area is minimum. Significantly no or minimum scar tissue with less retraction of rectal mucosa. [14] Our study revealed that postoperative pain was graded 0-1 on Visual analogue scale.

There was a marked improvement in preoperative symptoms in more than 80% of patients, and shrinkage of hemorrhoids was seen in more than 85-87% of the patients within three months to four months of the procedure.

The common postoperative complications in laser surgeries include delayed bleeding, presence of urinary retention, painful defecation, fistula, acute infection fissure, anal stenosis, fecal incontinence, and postoperative thrombosis. None of mentioned complications were observed in any of our patients within 6 months and 1 year after surgery.

Sowula reports no cases of postoperative bleeding during the follow-up. He states that the patients who were treated with laser therapy had a much more facilitated postoperative period and that the complications of these methods were very rare. [15] Leff claimed that wound healing was observed in all cases, and it was inferred that Hemorrhoidoplasty with lasers did not promote any adverse effects of surgery on the patients. [16] In another experiment performed by Zahir on 50 patients treated by laser therapy, pain alleviation was reported to be up to 65%. [17]

Conclusion: Lasers in hemorrhoids of grade 2 and grade 3 could be a secure, compelling, and effortless technique. Besides, this technique is also minimally invasive, does not require anesthesia, can be performed as an outpatient procedure, has the advantage of short hospital stay, and faster recuperation. So they can be an alternative to the

usual hemorrhoidectomy. Lasers are effective and safe in case of anal lesions and are comparable with other conventional methods of surgery. Nonetheless, further studies in this field are to be done.

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